

The Influence of Audio Visual Media on the Science Learning Outcomes of Class V Students of State Elementary School 095552 Jl. Asahan

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords : Audio Media
Visual, Results Study

Received : 26, August

Revised : 10, September

Accepted: 15, October

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ABSTRACT

Based on the results of observations that have been seen during the PPL period in this school, the results show that teachers very rarely use teaching aids or learning media in teaching in the classroom so that students become less active in following the lessons given by the teacher, so that learning outcomes which was achieved by fifth grade students It is still considered beautiful because it has not yet reached the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM) value. The type of research used in this research is quantitative, the population of this research is all class V students at SD Negeri 095552 Jl.Asahan totaling 26 students. Saturated sampling technique, the sample in this study consisted of all class V of SD N 095552 Jl. Asahan, totaling 26 students. The research results show that student learning outcomes using audio-visual media are in the good category. The results of the t distribution test at a significant level ($\alpha = 0.05$) $dk = N-1=26-1=25$, namely $t_{count} > t_{table}$, then the t distribution data with the result is $39.442 > 2.060$, so it can be said that there is a significant influence. The results and table of the t test prove that there is an influence of audio visual media (X) on learning outcomes (Y) with the results $r_{count} > r_{table}$ with the results $t_{count} > t_{table}$ $39.442 > 2.060$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the foundation of a country. Education is able to create quality resources who have good knowledge and skills. The world of education cannot be separated from the influence of the rapid development of information technology from time to time. This requires the world of education to continuously align changes and advances in technology with efforts to improve the quality of teaching, especially orientation by utilizing technology, information and communication as a means for the teaching and learning process in the school environment. Education is an important factor in the function of forming better quality humans and plays a major role in training people to become superior.

According to Republic of Indonesia Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System article 3 says "National education functions to develop abilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in order to make the life of the nation intelligent, aimed at developing the potential of students to become human beings who believe and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, be healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent and become democratic and responsible citizens."

The research carried out by Eiriika Wulansarii (2019) with the title "The influence of visual audio media on students' IIPA learning outcomes at SDN 101 Kota Beingkulu" this research proves that there is an influence of visual audio media on students' learning outcomes in subjects IIPA class IiV at Neigeirii Elementary School 101 Beingkulu City. This can be seen from the results of the hypothesis using the "t" test obtained, $t = 3.252$ compared to the t table with df 50 at the 5% significance level, namely 2.008. The definition of $t_{hitung} > t_{tabel}$ ($3.252 > 2.008$) which means H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

So, it can be concluded that with relevant media, science learning will run as optimally as possible. From this background review, the researcher will study through experimental research with the title "The Influence of Using Audio Visual Media on Science Learning Outcomes for Class V Students at State Elementary School 095552 Jl. Asahan".

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. Audio Visual Media

According to Ratnawatii et al, (2021:86) Visual audio media is a modern instructional media that is in line with the balance of modern times, media that can be seen and heard.

According to Suleiman (2022:11) Visual audio media are tools that are "audible" meaning they can be heard and tools that are "visible" meaning they can be seen.

From several expert opinions, it can be assumed that visual audio media is media that contains sound and image elements which are used as intermediaries in conveying messages from learning materials to achieve learning objectives because the way the content is read in the mechanism of the material being conveyed is different, there are those are quick to use audio

media (sightings) and there are also those who are quick to use visual media (sightings), so that's why it's easy to use visual audio media.

B. Learning outcomes

According to Dakhii (2020:468) learning outcomes are achievements that students achieve academically through tests and assignments, activeness in asking questions and answering questions that support the achievement of these learning outcomes.

From the above analysis, it can be concluded that student learning outcomes are changes in the attitudes and behavior of the students themselves as they receive the lessons provided by the teacher or individual.

C. Understanding IPA

According to Cariin and Sund (Sujana 2014:4) science is a systematic knowledge, generally valid, and takes the form of a collection of data results or observations and eikspeiriimein.

Sujana (2014: 4) states that natural science is a science that studies the natural world as it is, as well as the events that occur in it which are balanced by experts through a series of scientific processes carried out in a rigorous manner and be careful.

RESEARCH METHODS

Study This carried out at SD Negeri 095552 Jl.Asahan which is located at Jalan Asahan Km.5, Kec . Siantar in odd semesters year teachings 2023/2024. Study This use approach quantitative . Study This use method experiment with design study *Pre Experimental Design* use *One Group Pre-test Post-test* . Design study This only involve One class with give *pre-test* and *post-test* . Population study This is all over student class V SD Negeri 095552 Jl. Asahan which consists of from One class totaling 26 students . Retrieval technique sample in study This is *Total Sampling* , so sample in study This is amount whole class V, totaling 26 students .

Table 1. One Group Pretest Post Test Research Design

Pretest	Treatment	Posttest
O ₁	X	O ₂

Deep data collection techniques study this is tests in the form of question choice multiple. For determined item question instrument the worthy For given so moreover formerly done validation instrument. Test results are available tested try Then given to the class experiment. Data analysis techniques used For test hypothesis study namely the t test. Before the t test is carried out moreover formerly A prerequisite test is carried out , namely the normality test use formula *Shapiro-Wilk* and homogeneity test use formula sample t test and Anova.

RESULTS

Research results with Using audio- visual media is applied to students each other Work same , have ability in bear responsibility answer results Work group capable bring together ideas and thoughts, students more dare, train student share science. With thereby every student will a feeling of dependence arises positive so that matter the will influence results Study student class V Viewed from facet mark show that exists difference results Study student V class after given treatment of audio-visual media learning models. *Pretest* results obtained an average of 40.38 after given treatment the average result is obtained *posttest* as big as 83.07.

Before testing the hypothesis done moreover formerly prerequisite tests are carried out namely the normality test and homogeneity test . Based on the data normality test using formula *Shapiro- Wilk* Which presented in the table following.

Table 2. Normality Test Results

Normality Test						
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistics	Df	Sig.	Statist ics	df	Sig.
PRE TEST	,176	26	,037	,925	26	,058
POST TEST	,158	26	,095	,946	26	,189
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction						

From table 1 the results of the normality test obtain significance at *pretest* of 0.058 and significance at *posttest* of 0.189 with sample of 26 students . Viewed from results taking decision so can concluded that *pretest* and *posttest* data normally distributed because results. The significance obtained was > 0.05

Furthermore done testing homogeneity. Based on the data homogeneity test, it is used to find out whether several population variants are the same or not. This test was carried out as a requirement in the independent sample t test and Anova analysis which is presented in the table following.

Table 2. Homogeneity Test Results

Test of Homogeneity of Variances			
Pre-test			
Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
1,371	4	20	280

Data from table 2 obtained a significance value of 0.280 . Based on the basis of homogeneity test decision making, it can be concluded that the data is homogeneous where $0, 280 > 0.05$.

After the prerequisite tests are carried out, the t test analysis is carried out. A summary of the results of the t test analysis is presented in the following table.

Table 4. T-test results
Homogeneity Tests

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					Q	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	PostTest - Pretest	42,692	5,519	1,082	40,463	44,922	39,442	25	,000

Based on table 4 above, it is found that $t = 39.442$ with a significant level (2-tailed) of 0.000, the probability of significance is $t = 39.442 > 2.060$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This explanation shows that there is an influence of *Audio Visual Media on students' science learning outcomes Class V State Elementary School 095552 Jl. Asahan.*

DISCUSSION

Based on the pretest results, the average value of student learning outcomes was 4.0.38 with all students scoring below the KKM. Looking at the existing percentages, it can be said that the level of student learning outcomes before using the Influence of Using Audio Visual Media on Student Science Learning Outcomes relatively low. Furthermore, the average value of the posttest results is 8 3.07. So after using Audio Visual Media students have better learning outcomes than before using Audio Visual Media. After carrying out the pretest and posttest normality tests, a homogeneity test was carried out. Based on the homogeneity test, a significant value of 0.280 was obtained. Based on the results of the hypothesis test, it was obtained that the t value $> t_{table}$ ($t_{count} = 39.442 > t_{table} = 2.060$) and the significance was $0.00 < 0.05$, so H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. This means that there is an influence of the use of audio-visual media on students' science learning outcomes class v SDN 095552 Jl. Asahan.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the data presented in the previous section, the researcher concluded that the student learning outcomes before being given treatment, all students still had not reached the KKM, namely 26 students and after being given treatment, student learning outcomes increased, namely 26 students had scores above the KKM and based on the results Hypothesis test

with significance level = 0.05 and ttable of 2.060 tcount of 39.442. Thus tcount > ttable 39.442 > 2.060), it can be concluded that there is an influence of the use of Audio Visual Media on the Science Results of Class V Students at State Elementary School 095552 Jl.Asahan. So based on the results of the Hypothesis Test, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which indicates that there is an influence of the use of audio visual media on the science learning outcomes of class V students at State Elementary School 095552 Jl. Asahan

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